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DESIGNING OPEN INNOVATION PROBLEM-BASED PROJECTS: SOCIAL RELEVANCE, STUDENT EXPECTATIONS AND PRELIMINARY OBSERVATIONS

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ABSTRACT

In this concept paper, we present insights from an ongoing online interdisciplinary project with a “Technology and Migration” theme. The project is initiated by course coordinators from Medialogy and Techno-Anthropology at Aalborg University, is supported by the United Nations Refugee Agency (UNHCR) and is carried out by Bachelor and Master students from the two programs. We present the design of an open innovation problem-based educational activity, where different stakeholders

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facilitate student engagement in real-world issues regarding technology and migration. We present observations and results from a student survey, reporting on their motivations, expectations, and reactions to the format. We conclude with the expected outcomes and some preliminary results of the initiative.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Vision of Engineering Education

The modern engineer is capable of complex real-world problem solving, is entrepreneurial, is socially aware, and can flexibly work within and outside their discipline [1, 2]. Engineering educational programs at Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) must thus equip engineers for the contemporary landscape. One approach is to simulate real-world engineering work via problem-based student projects that incorporate interdisciplinarity (e.g. where students engage with the content or members of different disciplines) [3] and/or open innovation (e.g. where students engage with stakeholders external to HEIs) [4].

Examples of such cross-boundary student projects are the Innovation Course hosted by the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) [5, 6], the Learning in Interdisciplinary Focused Environment (LIFE) projects at Tallinn University [7], Ocean i3 at the University of Bordeaux [8], and the Open Innovation Laboratory at Tecnológico de Monterrey [4, 9]. In these programs, multidisciplinary groups of students (e.g. from engineering, science, humanities and design) create projects in response to a challenge or problem, and are encouraged to involve external stakeholders (e.g. end-users and industry experts). The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are often used to thematically unify the multidisciplinary members. In general, students develop their own projects, while guided by a mentor and a process framework (e.g. design thinking or similar).

While cross-boundary projects have produced positive results in developing key competencies in engineering [4, 5, 7] there are various key pedagogical considerations (e.g. high level of involvement of the facilitator(s), reflexive Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning implementation (CSCL), scaffolding interdisciplinarity) [2, 6]. To this end, pedagogical strategies need to be further explored. This paper shares one ongoing initiative by Aalborg University's Medialogy and Techno-Anthropology programs², supported by the United Nations Refugee

² *In the Medialogy program, students learn how to develop the technology behind advanced digital media products, such as advanced computer graphics, games, electronic music, animations, interactive art and entertainment. These media technologies are also seen from the user perspective, and therefore human-computer interaction, interaction design, psychology and related fields are also important [13]. The Techno-Anthropology program combines disciplinary elements from engineering and the humanities, as students explore the interaction between humans and technologies. It is a two way relationship in the sense that technologies hold intentionality and influence humans accordingly, while humans are not defenceless because technologies are designed, shaped, abused and domesticated by designers and users [14].*

Agency (UNHCR), to implement problem-based student projects that incorporate SDGs, interdisciplinarity and open innovation. We conduct a preliminary assessment of the format using observations and results from a student survey reporting on their motivations, expectations and reactions. We conclude with the expected outcomes and some preliminary results of the initiative.

1.2 The Technology and Migration Initiative

Problem-Based and Project-Based Learning (PBL) are the core of Aalborg University's pedagogy [10]. Every semester, groups of students independently work on problem-based projects, with guidance from academic supervisors and while attending three 5 ECTS courses that support their project work. These semester projects are obligatory modules for all students in all semesters, and they amount to 15 ECTS. Inspired by the SDGs, the "Technology and Migration" initiative (ongoing from February to June 2021) was co-developed by Medialogy and Techno-Anthropology course coordinators, to offer students an enriched project experience by adding further elements of social relevance, interdisciplinarity and open innovation.

Open innovation is understood as opening the innovation process to anyone, especially non-experts with a diverse background, and sharing the output of this process. Open innovation contributes to the circulation of knowledge and embodies science in tangible artifacts. The goal with the "Technology and Migration" initiative was to bring together academic staff and students from different disciplines and engage them in the transformation of knowledge to innovative solutions, prototypes, or artifacts as a response to the social challenges of migration. This initiative invited students and academics from Medialogy and Techno-Anthropology to get together, co-reflect, co-develop, and apply their knowledge to address a problem related to technology and migration and drawn from observation or from previous knowledge.

Bachelor's and master's students across the two programs were invited to create projects under the said overarching theme. Each group would then tackle the theme within the scopes of each group's focused interests and program's curriculum; this brings the opportunity for interdisciplinary collaboration and peer-learning, as student groups may offer peer-support as they progress with their projects. Open innovation is further incorporated by involving the UNHCR as an external expert. As facilitators, the course coordinators' key role is to support the collaborations between the students and with the UNHCR. Eighteen students are currently participating from four groups: one group from Medialogy (Bachelors; six students), two from Techno-Anthropology (Bachelors; four students respectively), and one from Techno-Anthropology (Masters, four students).

The PBL semester projects are part of the curriculum, they start in the beginning of each semester and span four months. The three supporting courses are given in the

first part of the semester in order to allow students to apply the knowledge obtained during these courses to their semester projects. Every group is assigned a supervisor for the semester, who is responsible for guiding the students and facilitating the process of working in the project. According to the PBL principles, the supervisor should not instruct students or take the decisions for them. For the “Technology and Migration” initiative, each group was assigned a supervisor from their own program but they had also access to mentors organizing this initiative. The student groups were meeting the mentors and the other groups working under the same theme once per week. An introduction seminar was organized in the beginning of the semester in order to introduce the students to the theme and the process. In the end of the semester, a final seminar was organized, where student groups presented their projects and got feedback from the mentors and the external stakeholder (UNHCR). Due to COVID-19 pandemic restrictions, all these activities and the collaboration among students of the same group were conducted online.

2 VECTORS OF COLLABORATION

2.1 Development and Planning

In September 2020, course coordinators from Medialogy initiated the idea for a cross-boundary semester project and developed a theme that was relevant to the curricula of programs that were invited to participate. Thus, the Technology and Migration theme and ideas for external stakeholders were included in the initial proposal sent to other university programs. With the participation of Techno-Anthropology, both programs identified several focus areas that were relevant to their students (Table 1). These focus areas were communicated in pitch emails to potential external stakeholders i.e., refugee agencies based in Denmark.

In February 2021, a meeting was held between course coordinators and the UNHCR to discuss collaboration possibilities. It was planned that the UNHCR would provide guidance on project topic development, participate in focused discussions with students, and provide project feedback. The meeting also provided invaluable feedback to the focus areas, each presented by the topic's direct representatives from the UNHCR branch in Denmark. Several officers from the World Bank were also present in the meeting; their facilitation was key for articulating different topics that might involve more than one leader within the agency. The three contemporary issues identified in the meeting and defined as the key challenges for the Technology and Migration initiative were: refugee data collection during COVID-19, digital inclusion, and e-learning and digital education (Table 1).

Starting a few weeks before the semester, information on the initiative was disseminated to students. The project was also presented during semester introduction lectures and explorative supervision sessions with bachelor's and master's students from both programs.

Table 1. Project themes development. First, course coordinators identified focus areas within “Technology and Migration” that were relevant to the Medialogy and Techno-Anthropology curricula. The UNHCR contributed key challenges related to these focus areas. Students then developed their project topics using both elements.

Focus areas identified by university course coordinators	Key challenges related to focus areas, identified by UNHCR	Project topics developed by students
<p>1. How can technology be used to measure and gather crucial information on the lives of displaced communities, and the types of challenges they face?</p> <p>2. How can technology help displaced populations and communities be part of a connected society?</p> <p>3. How can technology support education for refugees?</p> <p>4. How can technology be used to support long-term change?</p>	<p>1. Refugee data collection in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic</p> <p>2. Digital inclusion of refugees</p> <p>3. E-learning and digital education for refugees</p>	<p>1. App-based secondary education tool with gamification elements</p> <p>2. Technology assessment of e-learning systems used in refugee camps</p> <p>3. Privacy issues with collecting refugee data</p> <p>4. Migrant center in Copenhagen - ways of digital responsible data collection for funding applications.</p>

2.2 Implementation

While the students worked on their projects, the role of the facilitators was to support the students’ collaborative activities. Initially, this included creating an online discussion and knowledge-sharing space for students via Microsoft Teams, and hosting weekly support meetings for students. Facilitators also assisted students with contacting the UNHCR – to do so, one representative from Aalborg University and another from the UNHCR were responsible for collecting student questions, determining requirements, arranging future interactions, and arranging feedback sessions. These activities were not compulsory, and their sustainability was driven by the students themselves. Students were also free to initiate other forms of collaborative activities as inspired by their project work, such as interest group meetings.

In addition to knowledge-sharing, other types of support were also developed as the initiative progressed. For example, students required further guidance and support for field data collection. Additional contact with specific personnel (technical staff, teachers, and refugee students) in the refugee camps in Kenya, Jordan and

Denmark was necessitated by some groups. Thus, through an exploration into the authors' contacts network, it was possible to reach Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) representatives from the Education program in the biggest refugee camp in Jordan and technical staff in one refugee camp from Kenya. Subsequently, we gained access to staff from a refugee camp in Northern Uganda. These contacts would enable field empirical data collection remotely.

3 CURRENT OBSERVATIONS

3.1 Student Motivations for Participation

An online student survey distributed at the start of the initiative provides insight to the students' motivations for participation. The open survey was sent to the students working under the "Technology and Migration" theme and was focused on the motivation for participating in this initiative, their preferences on collaboration, and their expectations. The results from 18 responses are summarised here.

The biggest motivator was interest in the Technology and Migration theme itself. Seven students described the theme as an opportunity to produce a meaningful project with real-world impact. As one student writes, "*Migration issues are of the most vital and while there are also other problems that ought to be dealt with, I find the labour conditions for migrants and, generally the living conditions of people who try to make a new start, very important and fundamental in society*".

Four students also described the educational potential of the theme, that it "*fits well with my studies*" and allows them to gain "*general knowledge about... immigration and refugees*", "*tools and knowledge to engage in a very pertinent and important problem in the world*", and "*improving and applying the skills that I have in Techno-anthropology*". Other main motivations included interest in interdisciplinary collaborations ("*The collaboration between Techno-Anthropology and Medialogy, and as a software developer myself that intrigues me*"), guidance from mentors and experts, and being able to include the experience in their resumés.

In terms of collaborative activities, all students expressed interest in receiving feedback from external experts, 78.9% were interested in weekly support meetings, 78.9% were interested in presenting their final projects external experts, 74.7% were interested in discussions with students from other programs, 68.4% were interested in using a Microsoft Team for sharing resources, and 42.1% were interested in virtual social activities.

While such activities motivated these students to participate in the Technology and Migration initiative, we also experienced some difficulty in attracting involvement in the first place. For example, it was difficult to attract Medialogy students to participate (only one group joined), and within a month of the initiative's commencement, two students from Techno-Anthropology (Bachelors) left the initiative and their group to pursue a different theme. The lack of interest was largely due to the impression that the initiative would require additional responsibilities to complete their semester projects, since it would involve collaborating with

stakeholders beyond their individual student group (students are more accustomed to working only within their group). These additional activities and the personal initiative they demanded, though opportunities for developing key competencies, were unattractive to students who could not commit to them. As is the case for the two students who left after a period, students may also prefer a more straightforward project where the tasks were, to a higher extent, predefined by a supervisor. These doubts were likely compounded by the general uncertainty brought on by the abrupt transition to online learning and the pandemic context [11]. A lesson learned is that it is difficult to do interdisciplinary work that is not framed by the curriculum.

3.2 Considerations for Collaborating with External Stakeholders

Students were inspired by the input from the course coordinators and the UNHCR but formulated their own specific project topics (Table 1). Hence, they did not copy the ideas presented to them. This level of student engagement is aligned with Aalborg University's pedagogical model and its strategic aim of producing knowledge for real-world applications. It also fits well with study programs involved in this project, as they are all concerned with the societal effects of technologies. However, this approach by the students presented challenges to the UNHCR, who were not expecting this level of student engagement. On one occasion, the agency asked students to not pursue the project they had initially formulated, as they were already conducting a similar project. An important lesson is concerned with the need for a stronger pedagogical framework that specifically aligns external stakeholder and student expectations for collaboration. For example, facilitators should help UNHCR prepare specific challenges, rather than general themes, for student projects. Students generally delegate background data collection to the external stakeholder and do not exhaust other search possibilities. If the external stakeholder suggests challenges for student projects, they could be accompanied by background material.

3.3 Considerations for Active Online Learning

Considering the COVID-19 pandemic and its related restrictions, it was critical to foster a culture of open communication that can modulate, with relative ease, between professional and more casual tones. As previously mentioned, the authors had set up online information sessions as well as weekly support meetings via Microsoft Teams, and have used both to systematically engage all participants.

One result of these efforts has been an interdisciplinary collaboration initiated between one Medialogy (Bachelors) group and one Techno-Anthropology (Bachelors) group, as their projects were similar thematically and could potentially support one another ("App-based secondary education tool with gamification elements" and "Technology assessment of e-learning systems used in refugee camps"). The students created their own interest group channel in Microsoft Teams, crafted a code of conduct to harmonize working styles between the different groups, and are actively sharing insights and challenges at the weekly support meetings.

These actions are in line with the proposed culture of oscillation between professional and casual activities and are an example of open collaboration between

students from different disciplines, who are engaged to follow a shared academic interest in an interdisciplinary fashion. We propose that this approach to an open and online education is in line with the ongoing educational innovation and active distant learning, accelerated by reactions to the COVID-19 pandemic [12].

The relatively small number of participants has been helpful for facilitators to create an active online learning environment. With 18 students, the four facilitators could easily leverage a sense of community between the two disciplines, as well as facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration between smaller groups. Supported by the weekly support meetings and a somewhat shared academic vocabulary between Medialogy and Techno-Anthropology, students were able to form interdisciplinary groups and engage in interdisciplinary project work.

We learned from the project that the small number of participants and high level of engagement by the stakeholders contributed to a successful outcome. We did not, however, utilize the full potential of active online learning. Partly because we did not develop a tailor-made CSCL method that facilitates student project work and external collaborators priorities.

3.4 Lack of Funding to Support Students' Project Activities

When attempting to connect with experts and stakeholders closely related to refugee camps, we noticed that it might be necessary for the initiative to allocate funding to support activities that this contact and interaction may incur. For instance, funding may be needed to cover transportation to visit refugee camps (internationally, when it is allowed), to hire a local contact to remotely act on the behalf of the students in the refugee camp, to pay an interpreter service when there is a language barrier, and, very importantly, to support refugees and other informants with transportation costs, a per-diem, and access to the internet on their phones to hold interviews.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The Technology and Migration initiative by Aalborg University was designed as an enhanced educational experience for Medialogy and Techno-Anthropology students, by incorporating SDGs, interdisciplinarity and open innovation into problem-based student projects. While the initiative is still ongoing, observations so far indicate that the initiative has been an educational experience for students. For the first time for many of them, students are exercising key competencies associated with interdisciplinary collaboration and open innovation, such as communication, project management, conflict management, and leadership. As exemplified by their project topics (Table 1) and collaborative activities, students are exploring how their field of education could be used to address a real-world challenge and are learning about a socially relevant topic that does not traditionally arise in their field of education.

There were many pedagogical considerations involved in realising the Technology and Migration initiative. Adding to the highlighted considerations in section 1.1., we observed a stronger need for facilitator-student collaboration and reflection sessions. In general, it was useful for us coordinators to identify activities that students were

interested in at the start to ensure continued student engagement. For instance, weekly support meetings were arranged because students expressed a keen interest in them, and indeed these meetings have been well-attended and have played a key role in the initiative's success. As with any real-world cross-boundary project, collaboration challenges have arisen, such as managing the interests of various stakeholders. However, due to their inevitability, the challenges themselves serve as educational experiences for students. Once the initiative is completed, final student projects and a post-activity survey will be analysed for the final learning outcomes, student feedback, the relevance of collaborative work from different semesters and programs, and the complexity of collaboration or facilitation involving big organizational structures. A next step for the current initiative would be to integrate the lessons learned into the existing higher education infrastructure of Aalborg University.

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